

Classification of Games Used in Teaching English

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Abstract: This article is devoted to the importance of using games in teaching English. The article focuses on the role and types of games in teaching English classes. Teaching lessons through activities requires convenient storage and easy access to materials, objects, pictures, toys, games, conversation pieces, and other props. The article presents several examples of games for use in English classes. Using these interactive methods in English classes makes language learning more useful and meaningful. The use of active games aimed at developing students' thinking in lessons helps to achieve the goal set in the lesson.

Keywords: Methodologists, language games, approaches, communicative games, game method, grammar games, lexical games, phonetic games, spelling games.

Nowadays, there are various approaches to the classification of games in the classroom in a foreign language. Many methodologists abroad, including Andrew Wright, David Betteridge, Michael Buckby, and others, distinguish between language and communicative learning games.

Language games, according to their definition, are games in which grammatical and lexical language material is purposefully developed. Communicative games are ones in which the teacher's role is minimal, i.e. it should have no effect on the nature, content, or technique of speech engagement. The linguistic content, subject, interlocutors, and communication mechanisms are all chosen by the participants individually. The same foreign writers take a different approach to game division, recognizing the group aspect of the games. As a result, games for interaction and games for competitiveness are separated. The aim of interaction games can only be attained by the combined efforts of all group members.

In competitive games, groups or individuals compete in the speed and efficiency with which they solve the teacher-set goal.

At the same time, as reality demonstrates, all extant interaction games involve an element of competitiveness, as they are mostly team games. If there is no one to compete with, the usefulness of this type of game drops dramatically or disappears entirely (Solovova, 2010).

The games are classified as solitary, couple, group, team, or collective based on the number of participants. Individual games, it should be noted, assist the teacher

in implementing a customized approach to each student and represent a type of technique for the learner to "communicate" with one or more sources of information.

The other sorts of games include partners communicating with one another. These games use both an individual and a differentiated approach to the process of teaching a foreign language (Shaimetova, 2011).

M.F. Stronin offers another categorization, dividing games into two major classes. The first category comprises games that prepare the infant for the process of establishing speaking abilities, thus its name - "preparatory games". The second collection of activities, dubbed "creative games," aims to strengthen and develop verbal skills and capacities (Stronin, 1994). Both groups help the child's IQ and cognitive activity:

Preparatory games:

1. Grammar games

Main objective of grammar games is to emphasize the importance of the grammatical side of communication, specifically to educate the usage of speech patterns that involve certain grammatical problems.

Such games aid in the establishment of a natural setting for the usage of this speech sample, as well as the development of students' speech creative activity, initiative, and independence.

2. Lexical games

This kind of game is designed to work out lexical material, specifically instruction in the use of words in scenarios similar to those seen in the natural environment. They also allow you to familiarize yourself with the compatibility of words in the English language, promote speech-cognitive activity, and improve pupils' speech reactions.

3. Phonetic games

Phonetic games enhance and improve pronunciation skills: sentences intonation patterns, and phonemes.

4. Spelling games.

Spelling games are designed to help students practice writing English words. Some of these games are intended to train students' memory, while others are intended to introduce students to particular elements and patterns in the spelling of English words.

Creative games:

The objective of creative games is to educate students on the significance of a statement, to teach them to highlight the key concept in the flow of information, and to strengthen students' auditory memory. Such activities help pupils improve their speaking and listening abilities.

One of the goals of these games is to educate students how to respond throughout the communication process (Puchkova, 2005).

Role-playing games, competitive games, and dramatization games are examples of creative games (Ponomareva, 2009).

The presence of a single plot that corresponds to the selected communicative circumstance, as well as role relationships between communication players, are the major elements that govern the character of creative games (Mirzakhanova, 2012).

Therefore, despite the fact that both national and international methodologists base classifications on different qualities, all of the above forms of games stimulate and retain interest in foreign language communication. According to the categories, game exercises teach students to talk and behave in accordance with the game's rules for educational and methodological reasons.

After consideration of the topic of employing games in foreign language classes, we would like to emphasize the following provisions:

Classroom games should not be episodic and isolated.

A crosscutting gaming strategy that encompasses and integrates different sorts of activities in the process of teaching a foreign language is required.

The game technique is based on the construction of an imaginary situation and the acceptance of a certain role by a learner or a teacher. The game should alter the nature of connections between children and adults, who should not be coerced to do anything.

The instructor should not simply be the game's organizer and moderator. A crucial requirement is the capacity to play on an equal footing with the kid, to become a partner in the game, so that an outside viewer does not ruin the gaming environment.

The methods for playing games in the classroom should be designed with children's age and individual features in mind, as well as their language abilities, and should be focused on their growth.

Lessons in a foreign language should be understood by the instructor and should strive to develop the child's personality overall, in relation to his sensory, physical, and intellectual education.

Foreign language communication should be driven and intentional (Biboletova, 2012).

The more youngsters who immerse themselves in the environment of a game with unpredictable outcomes but clear rules, the more effective the learning will be.

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